

EQUALITY IN ACTION: WOMEN'S CONTRIBUTIONS TO SOCIETY

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Abstract: Women are making significant contributions to the development of science and technology, and their participation in these fields is becoming increasingly visible. This article examines women's influence on the world of high technology and highlights initiatives and reforms aimed at supporting women in Uzbekistan. It also gives examples of prominent women whose achievements and discoveries have left a noticeable mark on the scientific environment.

Keywords: technology, innovation, education, scientific achievements, women's contribution, development, reforms, resources, discovery, generations, programs, companies, significance, scientific community, awards, opportunities, role of women, digital age.

Аннотация: Женщины вносят существенный вклад в развитие науки и технологий, и их участие в этих сферах становится всё более заметным. В данной статье рассматривается влияние женщин на мир высоких технологий, а также освещаются инициативы и реформы, направленные на поддержку женщин в Узбекистане. Также приведены примеры выдающихся женщин, чьи достижения и открытия оставили заметный след в научной среде.

Ключевые слова: технологии, инновации, образование, научные достижения, женский вклад, развитие, реформы, ресурсы, открытие, поколения, программы, компании, значимость, научное сообщество, премии, возможности, роль женщины, цифровая эпоха.

Introduction

Despite their substantial impact on the scientific community, women's achievements in science often remain underappreciated. Historically, they have encountered numerous challenges in accessing higher education, earning academic qualifications, and building careers in research. Yet, in the modern world, many women continue to engage deeply with science, making valuable contributions across disciplines such as biology, medicine, physics, engineering, and information technology. Their efforts play a key role in driving innovation, expanding scientific knowledge, and supporting societal progress.

Nevertheless, gender disparities persist-especially in terms of career advancement opportunities and wage equality-highlighting the ongoing need for greater equity in the scientific field.

To ensure equal opportunities for men and women in science, it is necessary to continue to promote access to education, mentoring and financial support for women scientists. It is also important to continue to discuss and overcome stereotypes that prevent women from realizing their scientific ambitions. Raising awareness of women's contributions and creating equal opportunities will help to further develop the scientific community and achieve new heights in science. Historically, women have faced challenges in innovative technologies, but many have been able to overcome these obstacles and achieve great heights. For example, the famous Hollywood actress Hedy Lamar¹ was also a talented inventor: in 1942, she developed a frequency distribution system that later became the basis for the development of wireless technologies such as Bluetooth and Wi-Fi.

In addition, Ada Lovelace², daughter of the poet Lord Byron, is considered the first programmer in history. From the age of twelve, she was interested in mechanics, and in her mind she had the idea of designing a flying machine that would be powered by steam³. Her work on developing algorithms for Babbage's machine was the starting point for the birth of programming and had a great influence on the development of computer technology.

Discussions and results

Today, women continue to influence the world of technology innovation. They hold key positions in large technology companies, create start-ups and pioneer start-ups. Although the road to recognition and success can sometimes be difficult, women's contributions to innovation and technology remain important and vital to society.

Despite their significant achievements, they continue to face challenges and obstacles in their careers in the fields of science, technology, engineering and math. The achievements of women in science and technology are impressive: Marie Curie was the first woman scientist to win the Nobel Prize, and Jacqueline Figal followed suit with a Nobel in chemistry⁴. In today's world, women continue to make notable advances in scientific and technological fields, managing

¹ P. Kranzpiller. Hedy Lamarr (German). - Bergatreute: Eppe, 1997.

² Stephen Wolfram. Unraveling the story of Ada Lovelace (the first programmer in history).

³ Stephen Wolfram. Unraveling the story of Ada Lovelace (the first programmer in history) 40page

⁴ Sheryl Sandberg. Don't Be Afraid to Act: Women, Work and the Will to Lead. - Alpina Publishers. - 2014. Archived May 6, 2014. Archived May 6, 2014 at the Wayback Machine

projects and making significant discoveries. However, there are challenges preventing women from reaching their full potential in these fields. One challenge is the underrepresentation of women in leadership positions in science and technology companies.

Women professionals often face discrimination in technology. To overcome these challenges, it is necessary to strengthen awareness-raising efforts and to support and inspire young girls to pursue careers in science and technology. Promoting mentoring, creating equal opportunities and encouraging diversity in these fields are also important. Working to remove barriers faced by women in science, technology, engineering and math will open doors to talented minds, enrich the science and technology communities, and lead to new innovations and discoveries. It is worth noting that women are making impressive gains in the world of technology, despite the predominance of men in this field. Nowadays, more and more women are showing themselves as professionals and leaders in the field of technology.

For example, Sheryl Sandberg, the COO of Facebook, is recognized as one of the influential women in the tech industry worldwide. Her contributions to social media and digital technology are immense. Sheryl Sandberg has been one of the 50 "Most Influential Women in Business" according to Fortune magazine since at least 2008. In 2007, she ranked 29th and was the youngest woman on the list ⁵. Also worth mentioning is Ursula Burns, CEO and Chairman of Xerox, who demonstrates determination and influence in the tech industry. Moreover, women entrepreneurs, such as Elie Wisel, founder of Progyny, are breaking new ground in technology innovation⁶. Her efforts are focused on developing technologies in the healthcare industry, which has the potential to significantly improve the quality of life for many people. In this way, women are making a significant contribution to the field of technology, breaking new ground and inspiring the next generation of women to excel in this field.

Within this theme, it is worth noting the special programs that support women in business. These programs help develop entrepreneurial skills, improve financial literacy and provide access to the necessary resources to launch or expand a business. These initiatives help overcome barriers to starting a business and motivate women to become active entrepreneurs. Governments in various countries are also introducing special programs to support women in

⁵ Benner, Katie. "The Power 50 - Sheryl Sandberg (29) - FORTUNE". Money.CNN.com. Archived from the original on January 4, 2014. Date of access: July 22, 2010.

⁶ Sheryl Sandberg. Don't Be Afraid to Act: Women, Work and the Will to Lead. - Alpina Publishers. - 2014. Archived May 6, 2014. Archived May 6, 2014 at the Wayback Machine

business. These programs offer better credit terms, subsidies, training and counseling. Such efforts demonstrate a commitment to creating a favorable environment for women entrepreneurs and contribute to an increase in the number of successful women-owned businesses. All these measures are aimed at improving the economic status of women and creating conditions for their active participation in various business sectors.

Equal opportunities for women in entrepreneurship not only enrich the economy but also contribute to social development and sustainable growth of the society as a whole.

Conclusion

During the period of independence, women in Uzbekistan received special attention and support from the government. As part of the ongoing reforms, laws and programs have been adopted to protect women's rights and interests and to create equal opportunities in education, health care, the economy, and politics. The laws prohibit discrimination on the basis of sex and establish the basic principles of equal rights and opportunities for both sexes. The Government has also taken measures to educate and raise the profile of women. Considerable attention is also paid to health issues. The development of women's health in Uzbekistan is a medical priority. Conditions have been created for women's access to quality health care, and campaigns are being conducted to prevent women's diseases. A program to support women's entrepreneurship has been developed, loans are provided and training is provided, which contributes to the development of women's entrepreneurship in the country. And also in the field of education there was a reform where women could get free education in Master's and sometimes even Bachelor's degree.

Finally, women actively participate in the political life of Uzbekistan. The enshrinement of the principle of gender equality in the Constitution and the increase in the proportion of women in State institutions have enabled them to participate in decision-making, influence the political process and contribute to the development of the country.

Thus, over the years of independence, women in Uzbekistan have received considerable support from the State in various spheres of life, which has contributed to raising their social status and their level of participation in public life.

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